

Of all runs	success		average number		average
	rate	Max actions	of actions per	field	time in
	count	percentage	per field	field	msec
Long_mix_human	827	91.89%	82	1,050847458	55776
Long_mix_random	504	56.00%	17	1,799661017	71829
Long_text_human	900	100.00%	2	1,045454545	61937
Long_text_random	330	36.67%	32	1,590909091	73011
Short_mix_human	826	91.78%	42	1,045454545	18263
Short_mix_random	696	77.33%	22	2,045454545	24399
Short_text_human	880	97.78%	41	1,166666667	9720
Short_text_random	657	73.00%	17	1,416666667	9518

Of the successful runs	average		average	
	number	percentage of	number	percentage of
	of fields	fields filled	of fields	fields filled
Long_mix_human	58,7231	96.05%		
Long_mix_random	24,88095	40.89%		
Long_text_human	60,03333	100.00%		
Long_text_random	60,03333	100.38%		
Short_mix_human	18,85714	96.73%		
Short_mix_random	7,91667	40.65%		
Short_text_human	20,33295	90.94%		
Short_text_random	8,508371	44.11%		

actions	executed				submit			
	long mix	long text	short mix	short text	long mix	long text	short mix	short text
URL 1	0.399389	0.076041476	0.00238	0.111986872	0.001624652	3.95886E-07	6.55992E-06	1.924438432
URL 2	0.176128	0.657380427	0.39117	0.657380427	0.227643388	0.000242487	1	0.000823275
URL 3	0.399389	0.007786348	0.824496	0.283778048	0.002657523	3.22646E-08	0.004876906	1
URL 4	0.23885	2.51375E-05	0.297272	0.076041476	0.090968948	3.77421E-09	1.11365E-06	0.0384393
URL 5	0.668106	0.003904532	0.045945	0.657380427	1	7.74422E-06	0.004876906	0.00823275
URL 6	0.042067	0.505859178	0.375044	0.375043624	0.242908261	1.11365E-06	1.440695053	1.446383008
URL 7	0.375044	0.007786348	0.491783	0.399389395	0.001082623	1.92624E-05	1.610576304	0.011378477
URL 8	0.700686	1	0.47792	0.888302842	1.11365E-06	4.62547E-05	0.009823275	0.009823275
URL 9	0.01471	0.267502703	1	0.261175825	3.95886E-07	3.95886E-07	0.150323455	0.0384393
URL 10	0.001905	0.076041476	0.65738	0.363222313	0.002907748	7.74422E-06	0.070644825	7.74422E-06
URL 11	0.544168	0.657380427	0.292915	0.026577763	0.000532006	7.74422E-06	0.004876906	0.04351578
URL 12	0.65738	0.375043624	0.375044	0.300711047	1.17713E-05	1.01425E-09	0.028265769	0.00195754
URL 13	0.006522	9.19324E-06	0.10547	0.14737286	0.002270659	0.000107511	0.283899985	7.74422E-06
URL 14	0.049845	0.014710444	0.297272	0.026577763	2.99746E-06	1.31591E-08	1	0.640428787
URL 15	0.077609	9.19324E-06	0.334635	0.89183914	0.000380727	4.32346E-08	0.058137243	0.000107511
URL 16	0.012999	0.007786348	0.076041	0.076041476	0.007290358	1.92624E-05	0.070644825	1.11365E-06
URL 17	0.813005	0.026577763	0.946956	0.014710444	0.000723233	3.95886E-07	1.62890663	0.000532006
URL 18	0.037105	0.007786348	0.148449	0.076041476	4.19818E-06	2.99746E-06	#DEEL/01	#DEEL/01
URL 19	0.00236	0.007786348	0.267503	6.55751E-05	1.34187E-07	1.31591E-08	0.038365789	0.161124949
URL 20	0.006609	9.15234E-06	0.003183	0.689769657	0.036888426	1.25573E-11	0.005836317	0.000107511
URL 21	0.970516	8.12107E-09	0.778784	0.946855942	4.62547E-05	6.79456E-14	0.150323455	0.161124949
URL 22	0.325527	5.31674E-10	0.045945	0.139289366	0.165246607	1.31591E-08	0.518605016	#DEEL/01
URL 23	0.574247	0.000387782	0.222573	0.026577763	0.052052851	1.01425E-09	0.019517481	0.000566742
URL 24	0.418911	6.55751E-05	0.173777	0.574246708	0.198705600	1.01425E-09	4.62547E-05	0.001180996
URL 25	0.767468	2.51375E-05	1	0.657380427	4.36762E-05	1.34187E-07	0.313243773	7.74422E-06
URL 26	0	0	0	0	0.000242487	1.01425E-09	1.757091739	0.0002675243
URL 27	1	1.06701E-06	0.143287	0.888302842	0.003507385	2.53963E-10	1.686756227	0.161124949
URL 28	0.223773	1.06701E-06	0.28047	0.832813737	0.010396668	3.77421E-09	0.075569568	0.000379316
URL 29	0.564215	6.55751E-05	0.505859	0.183321226	8.01159E-05	1.92624E-05	0.070644825	4.36762E-05
URL 30	0.001905	0.076041476	0.610008	0.164609062	0.052052851	1.01425E-09	0.019517481	0.000566742
	11	21	5	6	22	30	12	21

Table with multiple columns containing numerical data, possibly representing coordinates or identifiers. The table is organized in a grid-like structure with rows and columns, some cells containing specific values like 'U', 'R1', 'R2', 'N1', 'N2', 'U1', 'U2' and others. Some cells are highlighted in green or red, and some contain mathematical expressions like 'z -0.032858495' or 'p 0.04206821'.

Table with 16 columns: URL, User, Role, Date, and various numeric columns (ID, Country, City, etc.). Contains 996 rows of data.

Table with columns for URL, IP addresses, and other metadata. Contains 1000 rows of data.

https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68286E+12 1,68286E+12 105 57 105 -6 6 no
https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68286E+12 1,68286E+12 105 57 105 -6 8 no
https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68286E+12 1,68286E+12 1682863246.02 1,682.863.266.787 105 57 21 16 2 yes
https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68286E+12 1,68286E+12 1,682.863.280.482 1,682.863.336.746 105 57 77 25 6 yes
https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68286E+12 1,68286E+12 1,682.863.349.369 1,682.863.378.543 105 57 35 20 3 yes
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https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68286E+12 1,68286E+12 105 57 105 -6 15 no
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https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68287E+12 1,68287E+12 1,682.869.003.053 1,682.869.030.987 105 53 33 22 3 yes
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https://webformsut.testar. long_mix random Random 2023-04-3 1,68287E+12 1,68287E+12 1,682.869.211.611 1,682.869.248.208 105 53 46 24 4 yes

https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	6	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	7	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.917.758.425	1.682.917.823.667	105	69	89	30	7	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1682917836.65	1.682.917.877.993	105	69	49	28	4	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.917.890.419	1.682.917.911.289	105	69	21	17	2	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.917.924.426	1.682.917.986.013	105	69	83	24	9	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	5	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.088.698	1682918131.77	105	69	53	34	2	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	7	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.235.923	1.682.918.270.106	105	69	41	23	3	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.283.423	1.682.918.317.383	105	69	40	21	5	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	8	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	9	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	6	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.600.659	1.682.918.667.434	105	69	92	37	6	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.680.015	1.682.918.746.467	105	69	91	45	5	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.760.084	1.682.918.790.945	105	69	36	28	3	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12			105	69	105	-6	6	no
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.893.894	1.682.918.960.878	105	69	90	36	7	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.918.974.413	1.682.919.011.642	105	69	46	23	5	yes
https://webformsut.testar.1.long_mix	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68292E+12	1,68292E+12	1.682.919.024.043	1.682.919.085.811	105	69	83	31	10	yes

https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.450.422	1.682.853.500.218	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.513.474	1.682.853.561.884	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.574.923	1.682.853.624.019	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.636.697	1.682.853.685.017	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.698.455	1.682.853.747.081	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.760.057	1.682.853.808.181	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.820.272	1.682.853.869.929	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.882.032	1.682.853.931.319	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.944.689	1682853993.12	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.854.005.258	1.682.854.053.404	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.854.066.698	1.682.854.116.184	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682854129.25	1.682.854.177.756	105	61	64	61	2	yes
https://we long_text	human_str	Human str	2023-04-30	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682854190.81	1.682.854.240.349	105	61	64	61	2	yes

https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	53	105	-6	7 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	53	105	-6	11 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	53	105	-6	9 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.361.497	1.682.912.397.726	105	61	63	25	8 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.410.529	1.682.912.456.435	105	61	84	38	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	10 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.537.826	1.682.912.565.843	105	61	44	23	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1682912578.69	1.682.912.608.235	105	61	48	24	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	11 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	9 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.757.848	1.682.912.788.627	105	61	50	26	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.800.851	1.682.912.833.682	105	61	55	24	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.846.587	1.682.912.875.249	105	61	47	21	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.912.888.113	1.682.912.934.771	105	61	84	38	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	9 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	14 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	7 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	10 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	10 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	11 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	9 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1682913432.85	1.682.913.463.819	105	61	49	21	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1682913477.33	1.682.913.510.883	105	61	55	29	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	7 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	10 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	9 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	7 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12			105	61	105	-6	13 no
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.913.872.085	1.682.913.899.888	105	61	45	28	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.913.912.205	1.682.913.939.432	105	61	41	22	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.913.952.871	1.682.913.985.932	105	61	55	27	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.913.997.965	1.682.914.051.635	105	61	99	36	7 yes
https://we long_text	random	Random	2023-05-0	1,68291E+12	1,68291E+12	1.682.914.064.866	1.682.914.116.267	105	61	92	40	7 yes

https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h23m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	13	no		
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h23m52s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	9	no		
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h24m31s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.477.315	1,682.839.492.038	45	23	18	3	yes	
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h24m59s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.505.524	1,682.839.522.321	45	20	23	10	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h25m30s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.536.191	1,682.839.554.589	45	20	27	9	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h26m02s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	20	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h26m41s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.606.531	1,682.839.616.711	45	20	14	5	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h27m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.630.344	1,682.839.642.252	45	20	10	4	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h27m29s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.654.705	1,682.839.670.611	45	20	21	7	7	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h27m58s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.683.375	1,682.839.703.109	45	20	30	13	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h28m30s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.716.504	1,682.839.741.472	45	20	41	11	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h29m09s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.754.662	1682839771.88	45	20	25	12	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h29m39s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.785.659	1,682.839.804.519	45	20	28	11	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h30m11s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.817.412	1,682.839.829.573	45	20	14	8	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h30m37s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.843.592	1,682.839.857.148	45	20	18	11	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h31m03s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.869.059	1,682.839.882.789	45	20	17	8	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h31m29s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.895.371	1,682.839.909.838	45	20	18	12	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h31m56s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.922.522	1682839941.82	45	20	29	11	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h32m28s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.954.329	1,682.839.967.386	45	20	16	6	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h32m55s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.839.981.337	1,682.839.990.202	45	20	8	4	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h33m17s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.003.773	1,682.840.010.966	45	20	6	2	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h33m37s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.023.383	1,682.840.042.884	45	20	29	9	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h34m10s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.056.725	1,682.840.066.451	45	20	9	5	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h34m32s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1682840078.72	1,682.840.097.561	45	20	28	8	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h35m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.110.033	1,682.840.123.625	45	20	17	11	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h35m31s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.136.795	1,682.840.154.609	45	20	26	16	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h36m02s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.168.351	1,682.840.181.769	45	20	17	8	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h36m27s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1682840193.7	1,682.840.212.157	45	20	26	10	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h37m00s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	20	45	-6	6	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h37m39s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.265.114	1,682.840.270.913	45	20	4	2	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h37m59s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.285.109	1,682.840.310.774	45	20	44	14	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h38m38s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.323.953	1,682.840.345.063	45	20	33	10	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h39m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1682840358.78	1,682.840.373.383	45	20	20	7	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h39m40s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	5	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h40m21s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.426.724	1,682.840.433.604	45	16	5	3	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h40m41s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h41m20s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.486.429	1,682.840.502.295	45	16	21	4	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h41m50s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	6	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h42m30s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.556.023	1,682.840.561.877	45	16	4	2	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h42m48s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.574.126	1682840592.11	45	16	26	8	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h43m19s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.605.246	1,682.840.619.615	45	16	20	7	8	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h43m46s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h44m26s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	10	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h45m05s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.710.634	1,682.840.719.104	45	16	7	5	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h45m26s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.732.048	1,682.840.740.518	45	16	8	5	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h45m47s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h46m27s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	10	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h47m06s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	6	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h47m44s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	8	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h48m23s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	5	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h49m02s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.840.948.745	1,682.840.965.609	45	16	24	10	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h49m32s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	7	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h50m11s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	5	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h50m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1682841057.34	1,682.841.073.594	45	16	24	7	7	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h51m20s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.086.519	1,682.841.104.133	45	16	27	6	9	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h51m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	11	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h52m29s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.154.587	1,682.841.170.443	45	16	23	6	7	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h52m58s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.184.023	1,682.841.197.164	45	16	16	7	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h53m24s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h54m03s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	16	45	-6	5	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h54m41s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.286.994	1682841296.9	45	16	10	4	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h55m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.309.838	1,682.841.323.764	45	16	19	7	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h55m30s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.336.515	1,682.841.350.192	45	16	18	10	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h55m57s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.363.052	1,682.841.374.254	45	14	13	6	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h56m22s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.388.656	1,682.841.407.095	45	14	27	6	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h56m53s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.419.642	1,682.841.437.645	45	14	26	10	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h57m25s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.451.085	1682841462.5	45	14	14	10	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h57m50s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.476.211	1,682.841.483.204	45	14	6	4	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h58m10s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	14	45	-6	7	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h58m49s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.534.987	1682841547.81	45	14	17	5	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h59m13s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	14	45	-6	15	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_09h59m50s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.596.311	1,682.841.606.314	45	14	11	4	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h00m13s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	14	45	-6	13	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h00m49s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.655.653	1,682.841.666.192	45	14	12	6	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h01m13s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	14	45	-6	11	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h01m50s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.716.096	1,682.841.726.069	45	14	10	5	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h02m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	14	45	-6	12	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h02m49s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.775.693	1,682.841.801.541	45	14	45	9	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h03m28s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.841.814.599	1,682.841.825.935	45	14	14	4	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h03m52s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12			45	14	45	-6	8	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random											

https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h16m36s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.602.123	1.682.842.622.421	45	21	33	13	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h17m09s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.635.841	1.682.842.653.315	45	21	25	13	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h17m40s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.666.417	1.682.842.690.289	45	21	39	14	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h18m16s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.702.793	1.682.842.713.667	45	21	12	7	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h18m41s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.727.074	1.682.842.741.575	45	21	19	9	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h19m07s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.753.451	1.682.842.768.1	45	21	20	9	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h19m35s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.781.766	1.682.842.793.23	45	21	13	4	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h20m00s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.806.627	1.682.842.828.04	45	21	38	12	7	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h20m35s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.841.837	1.682.842.866.841	45	21	44	14	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h21m14s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.879.945	1.682.842.894.892	45	21	20	7	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h21m42s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.908.596	1.682.842.919.469	45	21	12	6	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h22m06s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.932.088	1.682.842.953.22	45	21	34	13	5	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h22m40s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.965.898	1.682.842.987.861	45	21	36	13	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h23m14s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.842.997.861	1.682.842.1013.73	45	21	45	14	10	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h23m54s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.040.477	1.682.843.047.954	45	21	6	4	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h24m14s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.078.945	1.682.843.087.892	45	21	45	10	7	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h24m53s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.117.925	1.682.843.128.139	45	21	45	10	10	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h25m32s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.138.571	1.682.843.157.462	45	21	29	11	5	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h26m05s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.170.648	1.682.843.178.729	45	12	8	6	1	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h26m26s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.192.021	1.682.843.205.385	45	12	19	5	5	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h26m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.217.779	1.682.843.235.479	45	12	27	5	5	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h27m22s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.248.552	1.682.843.259.469	45	12	13	3	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h27m45s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.271.614	1.682.843.277.593	45	12	4	2	1	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h28m03s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.289.757	1.682.843.302.453	45	12	17	4	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h28m29s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.315.39	1.682.843.327.375	45	12	15	6	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h28m53s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.339.898	1.682.843.359.688	45	12	31	6	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h29m27s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.373.086	1.682.843.384.379	45	12	14	5	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h29m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.397.813	1.682.843.411.468	45	12	18	5	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h30m18s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.423.874	1.682.843.444.347	45	12	33	7	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h30m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.457.675	1.682.843.462.195	45	12	2	0	1	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h31m09s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.474.856	1.682.843.496.553	45	12	37	9	7	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h31m43s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.509.391	1.682.843.517.286	45	12	7	4	1	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h32m03s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.529.692	1.682.843.542.776	45	12	18	6	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h32m29s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.555.849	1.682.843.565.918	45	12	12	3	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h32m53s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.579.032	1.682.843.588.636	45	12	11	5	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h33m15s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.601.863	1.682.843.615.216	45	12	18	5	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h33m41s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.627.748	1.682.843.634.403	45	12	5	3	1	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h34m00s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.646.323	1.682.843.665.449	45	12	31	5	9	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h34m33s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.679.102	1.682.843.684.37	45	12	3	1	1	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h34m50s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.696.921	1.682.843.708.566	45	12	14	8	2	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h35m16s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.722.338	1.682.843.730.502	45	12	8	3	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h35m37s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.743.465	1.682.843.754.836	45	12	14	7	2	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h36m01s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.767.274	1.682.843.775.423	45	12	18	4	2	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h36m21s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.787.957	1.682.843.800.331	45	12	17	5	9	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h36m47s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.813.624	1.682.843.828.038	45	12	15	7	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h37m16s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.842.284	1.682.843.863.055	45	12	35	7	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h37m49s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.875.416	1.682.843.892.383	45	12	26	6	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h38m19s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.843.905.075	1.682.843.918.447	45	12	18	5	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h38m44s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.000.000	1.682.844.000.000	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h39m23s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.039.615	1.682.843.991.403	45	23	35	11	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h39m58s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.079.102	1.682.844.094.37	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h40m37s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.043.329	1.682.844.062.67	45	23	28	8	9	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h41m09s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.082.000	1.682.844.082.000	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h41m49s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.115.43	1.682.844.136.732	45	23	34	14	8	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h42m24s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.150.218	1.682.844.175.076	45	23	41	13	11	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h43m02s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.187.946	1.682.844.206.114	45	23	27	10	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h43m34s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.223.000	1.682.844.223.000	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h44m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.259.622	1.682.844.278.785	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h44m50s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.296.622	1.682.844.318.785	45	23	36	15	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h45m25s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.331.552	1.682.844.356.853	45	23	44	13	7	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h46m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.367.274	1.682.844.382.000	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h46m43s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.400.000	1.682.844.400.000	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h47m21s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.447.686	1.682.844.471.016	45	23	37	15	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h47m58s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.484.84	1.682.844.494.714	45	23	10	2	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h48m22s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.508.14	1.682.844.530.655	45	23	36	14	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h48m58s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.543.795	1.682.844.566.401	45	23	36	11	6	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h49m33s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.582.000	1.682.844.582.000	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h50m13s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.618.831	1.682.844.629.914	45	23	12	4	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h50m36s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.642.265	1.682.844.663.912	45	23	33	14	5	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h51m10s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.676.871	1.682.844.699.569	45	23	38	13	9	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h51m45s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.711.062	1.682.844.727.854	45	23	23	6	4	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h52m14s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.743.465	1.682.844.754.836	45	23	45	10	5	no
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h52m53s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.779.854	1.682.844.789.781	45	23	10	5	3	yes
https://we short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_10h53m17s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1.682.844.808.203	1.682.844.814.43	45	23	12			

https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h53m20s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.006.478	1.682.852.013.872	45	13	6	3	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h53m40s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.027.181	1.682.852.036.301	45	13	9	4	2	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h54m02s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.049.062	1.682.852.061.329	45	13	16	5	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h54m27s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	21	45	-6	8	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h55m07s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.113.605	1.682.852.127.396	45	21	18	7	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h55m33s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.139.669	1.682.852.147.036	45	21	6	2	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h55m52s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.159.017	1.682.852.180.224	45	21	32	11	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h56m27s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.194.025	1.682.852.208.016	45	21	17	7	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h56m55s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.221.454	1.682.852.237.258	45	21	22	5	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h57m24s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.250.233	1.682.852.269.827	45	21	30	11	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h57m56s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682852282.33	1.682.852.293.294	45	21	12	5	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h58m21s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.307.299	1.682.852.321.571	45	21	19	10	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h58m47s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682852333.84	1.682.852.341.501	45	21	6	2	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h59m08s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.354.624	1.682.852.377.314	45	21	37	14	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_12h59m44s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	21	45	-6	7	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h00m23s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.429.348	1.682.852.443.957	45	21	20	10	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h00m50s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.456.096	1.682.852.470.384	45	21	19	8	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h01m17s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.483.886	1.682.852.503.315	45	21	30	15	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h01m51s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.517.499	1.682.852.535.645	45	21	25	15	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h02m22s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.548.633	1.682.852.567.041	45	21	28	15	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h02m53s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	21	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h03m31s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.618.015	1.682.852.636.929	45	21	29	9	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h04m03s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.650.099	1.682.852.666.212	45	21	22	10	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h04m32s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.679.019	1682852695.82	45	21	24	12	8	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h05m02s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.708.279	1682852728.59	45	21	31	16	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h05m35s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.742.076	1.682.852.757.575	45	21	22	8	8	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h06m05s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.771.499	1.682.852.784.065	45	21	15	8	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h06m31s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.797.165	1.682.852.817.344	45	21	31	14	6	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h07m03s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.830.307	1.682.852.843.947	45	21	18	8	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h07m30s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.856.419	1682852880.1	45	21	40	15	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h08m06s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	21	45	-6	7	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h08m44s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.930.781	1.682.852.940.446	45	21	9	5	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h09m06s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.953.007	1.682.852.962.945	45	21	10	2	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h09m29s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.976.044	1.682.852.989.167	45	27	16	9	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h09m55s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.002.153	1.682.853.028.511	45	27	44	13	7	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h10m35s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.042.103	1.682.853.054.606	45	27	15	6	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h11m00s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682853066.85	1682853077.39	45	27	10	4	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h11m24s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.090.652	1.682.853.114.923	45	27	40	13	9	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h12m01s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.127.568	1.682.853.145.515	45	27	26	9	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h12m31s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.158.063	1.682.853.177.578	45	27	28	8	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h13m04s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	8	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h13m42s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.228.425	1682853247.33	45	27	29	10	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h14m14s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	16	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h14m52s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.298.734	1.682.853.315.565	45	27	23	11	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h15m22s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.328.835	1.682.853.350.831	45	27	36	13	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h15m57s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.363.736	1.682.853.382.228	45	27	26	9	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h16m28s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.395.136	1.682.853.413.946	45	27	28	12	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h17m00s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.426.562	1.682.853.443.861	45	27	25	13	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h17m30s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.457.149	1.682.853.472.997	45	27	20	12	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h17m59s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.485.629	1.682.853.507.982	45	27	36	11	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h18m35s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	9	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h19m14s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.560.995	1.682.853.583.124	45	27	34	12	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h19m49s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	5	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h20m28s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.635.259	1682853648.96	45	27	17	10	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h20m55s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	7	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h21m33s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	7	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h22m13s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.739.666	1.682.853.752.422	45	27	15	7	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h22m39s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.764.967	1682853775.87	45	27	11	5	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h23m02s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.788.483	1.682.853.812.179	45	27	38	17	3	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h23m38s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	27	45	-6	10	no
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h24m18s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.864.619	1.682.853.879.697	45	27	21	10	4	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h24m47s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682853893.37	1.682.853.915.657	45	27	35	12	5	yes
https://we_short_mix	random	Random	2023-04-30_13h25m22s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.853.928.916	1.682.853.950.246	45	27	34	14	6	yes

https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h44m42s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.086.091	1.682.801.107.449	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h45m16s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.120.278	1.682.801.142.164	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h45m52s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.156.244	1.682.801.178.087	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h46m27s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.191.164	1.682.801.212.698	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h47m03s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.226.534	1.682.801.248.447	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h47m38s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.261.773	1.682.801.283.777	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h48m13s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.296.873	1682801318.53	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h48m47s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.331.325	1.682.801.353.299	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h49m23s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.366.617	1.682.801.388.909	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h49m58s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.402.576	1.682.801.424.194	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h50m33s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.437.447	1.682.801.459.256	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h51m09s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.472.597	1.682.801.494.788	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h51m44s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.507.588	1.682.801.529.462	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h52m18s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.542.147	1.682.801.563.744	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h52m53s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.576.801	1.682.801.598.184	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h53m27s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.610.937	1.682.801.632.836	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h54m01s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.645.439	1.682.801.666.659	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h54m36s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.679.878	1.682.801.701.625	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h55m11s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.714.966	1.682.801.736.796	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h55m46s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.749.805	1.682.801.773.377	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h56m22s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.785.723	1.682.801.807.644	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h56m57s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.820.974	1.682.801.842.833	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h57m31s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.855.133	1.682.801.876.927	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h58m06s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.890.247	1.682.801.912.572	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h58m42s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682801926.15	1.682.801.947.871	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h59m17s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.961.155	1.682.801.977.249	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 22h59m46s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.801.990.296	1.682.802.006.458	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h00m15s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.018.655	1.682.802.035.018	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h00m43s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.047.021	1682802063.46	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h01m13s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.077.337	1.682.802.094.189	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h01m44s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.107.731	1.682.802.124.116	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h02m14s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.137.831	1.682.802.154.993	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h02m44s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.168.256	1.682.802.185.151	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h03m15s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.198.905	1.682.802.215.186	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h03m44s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.228.638	1.682.802.245.669	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h04m14s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.257.603	1.682.802.273.942	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h04m43s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.287.085	1682802303.09	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h05m12s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.316.476	1.682.802.332.623	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h05m41s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.345.105	1.682.802.361.268	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h06m11s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.374.895	1682802391.11	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h06m41s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.405.443	1.682.802.421.215	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h07m11s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.434.443	1.682.802.450.072	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h07m40s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.463.754	1.682.802.480.558	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h08m10s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.494.012	1682802510.15	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h08m39s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.522.876	1.682.802.538.514	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h09m09s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.552.927	1682802569.29	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h09m38s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.582.389	1.682.802.598.975	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h10m08s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.612.541	1682802628.38	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h10m38s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.641.734	1.682.802.658.089	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h11m08s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.671.813	1.682.802.687.741	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h11m37s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.700.791	1.682.802.716.562	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h12m05s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.729.293	1.682.802.745.342	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h12m34s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.758.123	1.682.802.773.976	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h13m03s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.787.146	1.682.802.803.873	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h13m33s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.817.069	1682802833.06	45	19	22	19	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h14m01s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.845.268	1.682.802.863.423	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h14m33s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.876.633	1.682.802.895.154	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h15m04s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.908.304	1.682.802.926.421	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h15m36s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.939.744	1682802958.53	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h16m08s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.802.971.408	1.682.802.989.643	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h16m39s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.003.378	1.682.803.021.801	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h17m10s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.034.348	1.682.803.052.951	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h17m42s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.065.346	1.682.803.083.833	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h18m13s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.096.708	1.682.803.115.022	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h18m44s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682803128.21	1.682.803.146.955	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h19m16s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.160.676	1.682.803.179.068	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h19m47s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682803191.06	1.682.803.210.576	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h20m19s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.223.433	1.682.803.241.742	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h20m51s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.255.181	1.682.803.273.552	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h21m23s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.286.902	1.682.803.305.107	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h21m54s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.318.402	1.682.803.336.642	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h22m26s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682803350.29	1.682.803.369.019	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h22m58s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.381.978	1.682.803.401.065	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h23m29s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682803413.21	1.682.803.431.654	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h24m00s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.444.249	1.682.803.462.663	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h24m31s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.475.105	1.682.803.493.765	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h25m02s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.505.904	1.682.803.524.743	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h25m34s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.537.406	1.682.803.555.711	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h26m05s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.803.569.116	1.682.803.587.102	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29 23h26m36s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682803600.49	1.682.803.619.135	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://										

https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h35m31s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.134.825	1.682.804.146.555	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h35m55s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.159.348	1.682.804.170.855	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h36m20s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.183.507	1.682.804.194.982	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h36m44s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.208.602	1682804220.41	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h37m09s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.233.387	1.682.804.245.109	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h37m34s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.258.553	1.682.804.270.109	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h37m59s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.283.236	1.682.804.294.831	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h38m23s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.306.824	1.682.804.318.111	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h38m47s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.331.437	1.682.804.343.752	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h39m13s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682804356.9	1.682.804.368.663	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h39m38s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.382.437	1.682.804.394.029	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h40m03s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.407.264	1.682.804.419.266	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h40m27s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.430.799	1.682.804.442.444	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h40m51s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682804455.22	1.682.804.466.668	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h41m16s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.479.861	1.682.804.491.136	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h41m40s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.504.437	1.682.804.516.215	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h42m04s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.528.006	1.682.804.540.121	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h42m29s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682804553.29	1.682.804.574.288	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h43m03s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.587.633	1.682.804.608.037	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h43m38s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.621.864	1.682.804.642.598	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h44m11s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.655.746	1.682.804.676.426	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h44m45s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.688.908	1682804709.79	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h45m19s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.723.015	1.682.804.743.965	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h45m53s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.756.424	1.682.804.777.123	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h46m26s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.790.241	1.682.804.811.169	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h47m01s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.825.614	1.682.804.845.638	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h47m34s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.858.301	1.682.804.879.267	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h48m09s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.892.812	1.682.804.913.659	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h48m42s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.926.558	1.682.804.947.374	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h49m16s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.960.038	1.682.804.980.655	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h49m49s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.804.993.057	1.682.805.013.617	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h50m22s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.025.772	1.682.805.046.368	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h50m54s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.058.038	1.682.805.078.319	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h51m27s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.090.802	1.682.805.111.384	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h52m00s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.124.177	1.682.805.144.512	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h52m34s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682805157.66	1.682.805.178.387	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h53m08s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.191.886	1.682.805.212.325	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h53m41s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.225.158	1.682.805.245.469	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h54m14s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.258.223	1.682.805.278.986	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h54m48s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.291.901	1.682.805.312.256	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h55m22s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.325.425	1.682.805.345.784	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h55m55s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12			45	27	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h56m34s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.397.903	1.682.805.418.264	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h57m07s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.430.644	1682805451.21	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h57m41s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.464.722	1.682.805.484.963	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h58m14s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682805497.57	1.682.805.517.916	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h58m46s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.529.986	1.682.805.551.089	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h59m21s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.564.855	1.682.805.580.412	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-29_23h59m50s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.593.993	1.682.805.610.089	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h00m19s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.622.946	1.682.805.639.447	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h00m49s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12			45	18	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h01m26s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.689.862	1.682.805.705.597	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h01m55s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.719.339	1682805734.82	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h02m23s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.747.154	1.682.805.762.249	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h02m51s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.775.165	1.682.805.791.091	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h03m20s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.804.566	1.682.805.820.238	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h03m49s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12			45	18	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h04m26s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.870.691	1.682.805.885.895	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h04m54s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.897.929	1682805914.09	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h05m23s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.926.772	1.682.805.942.428	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h05m52s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.955.802	1.682.805.971.463	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h06m21s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.805.984.945	1.682.806.000.618	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h06m50s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.013.885	1.682.806.029.191	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h07m18s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.042.198	1.682.806.057.227	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h07m46s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.069.905	1.682.806.085.507	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h08m14s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682806098.38	1.682.806.113.724	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h08m42s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682806126.52	1682806141.8	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h09m10s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682806153.86	1.682.806.169.474	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h09m39s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.182.729	1.682.806.198.765	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h10m08s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.212.131	1.682.806.227.366	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h10m36s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.240.424	1.682.806.256.388	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h11m05s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.268.953	1.682.806.284.628	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h11m32s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.296.447	1.682.806.312.017	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h12m01s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.325.014	1.682.806.341.266	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h12m30s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1682806353.97	1.682.806.369.426	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h12m58s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.381.744	1.682.806.396.992	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h13m27s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.410.325	1682806425.67	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h13m55s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.439.182	1.682.806.450.319	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h14m19s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.463.186	1.682.806.473.884	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h14m42s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.485.835	1.682.806.496.457	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h15m05s	1,6828E+12	1,6828E+12	1.682.806.508.304	1682806519.05	45	10				

https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h22m07s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.806.930.972	1,682.806.941.782	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h22m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.806.954.295	1682806965.4	45	10	13	10	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h22m54s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.806.977.933	1,682.806.988.553	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h23m18s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.001.651	1682807012.08	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h23m41s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.025.727	1,682.807.036.051	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h24m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.048.316	1,682.807.059.138	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h24m28s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.072.096	1,682.807.082.512	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h24m51s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.095.327	1,682.807.106.233	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h25m14s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.118.202	1,682.807.128.668	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h25m37s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.140.979	1682807162.78	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h26m12s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.176.215	1,682.807.196.924	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h26m45s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.209.601	1,682.807.231.313	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h27m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.243.827	1,682.807.265.679	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h27m54s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682807278.26	1,682.807.300.053	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h28m29s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.313.617	1,682.807.334.943	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h29m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.348.089	1,682.807.369.882	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h29m38s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.382.705	1,682.807.403.665	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h30m12s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.416.001	1682807437.26	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h30m46s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.450.233	1,682.807.471.966	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h31m21s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.484.839	1,682.807.506.312	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h31m55s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.519.458	1,682.807.541.718	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h32m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682807554.73	1,682.807.576.077	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h33m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.588.945	1,682.807.610.468	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h33m39s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.623.327	1,682.807.644.656	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h34m14s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.657.891	1,682.807.679.065	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h34m48s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682807691.81	1,682.807.713.832	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h35m22s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.726.593	1,682.807.747.582	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h35m57s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682807760.91	1,682.807.782.255	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h36m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.795.839	1,682.807.817.569	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h37m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.829.165	1,682.807.850.697	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h37m39s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.863.687	1,682.807.884.914	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h38m13s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682807897.2	1,682.807.918.655	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h38m47s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.931.447	1,682.807.952.951	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h39m22s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.807.966.373	1,682.807.987.593	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h39m56s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.000.473	1,682.808.022.372	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h40m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.034.297	1,682.808.056.298	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h41m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.069.638	1,682.808.091.393	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h41m40s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.103.939	1,682.808.125.784	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h42m15s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682808139.08	1,682.808.160.457	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h42m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.173.132	1,682.808.190.041	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h43m18s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.202.455	1,682.808.219.219	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h43m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.232.955	1,682.808.250.246	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h44m19s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.262.936	1,682.808.279.915	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h44m48s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.292.727	1,682.808.309.562	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h45m19s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.323.294	1,682.808.341.064	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h45m50s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.354.017	1,682.808.371.175	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h46m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.384.133	1,682.808.401.163	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h46m50s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.414.164	1,682.808.431.425	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h47m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.443.927	1,682.808.460.973	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h47m50s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.474.705	1,682.808.492.349	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h48m21s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.505.469	1,682.808.522.851	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h48m52s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12			45	21	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h49m29s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.572.976	1,682.808.590.584	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h49m59s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.603.692	1682808620.65	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h50m29s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.633.442	1,682.808.650.968	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h51m00s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.664.181	1,682.808.681.382	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h51m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.695.061	1682808712.66	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h52m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.725.054	1,682.808.742.126	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h52m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.755.413	1,682.808.773.018	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h53m00s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.784.759	1,682.808.802.149	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h53m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.815.005	1,682.808.832.239	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h54m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.845.638	1,682.808.862.728	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h54m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.875.177	1,682.808.891.959	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h55m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.904.625	1682808922.15	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h55m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.935.916	1,682.808.953.166	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h56m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.966.335	1,682.808.983.828	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h56m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.808.995.919	1,682.809.013.496	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h57m03s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.027.108	1,682.809.045.079	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h57m34s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.057.641	1,682.809.075.163	45	21	24	21	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h58m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.088.445	1,682.809.106.975	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h58m35s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.119.303	1,682.809.138.066	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h59m07s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.150.866	1682809169.47	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_00h59m38s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.182.826	1,682.809.201.283	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h00m10s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682809214.1	1,682.809.232.399	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h00m39s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.243.691	1,682.809.261.683	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h01m10s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.273.897	1,682.809.292.504	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h01m41s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.305.611	1,682.809.324.104	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h02m13s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.337.533	1,682.809.355.605	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h02m45s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.368.985	1,682.809.387.278	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30_01h03m15s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1,682.809.399.521	1,682.809.418.423	45	23</				

https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h13m27s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.011.894	1.682.810.030.665	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h13m59s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.043.219	1.682.810.061.666	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h14m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.075.122	1.682.810.093.385	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h15m02s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.106.394	1.682.810.124.848	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h15m33s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.137.659	1682810156.26	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h16m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.168.856	1.682.810.187.644	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h16m37s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.201.068	1.682.810.219.782	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h17m09s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.233.175	1.682.810.252.159	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h17m41s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.264.669	1.682.810.283.222	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h18m12s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.296.539	1.682.810.315.268	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h18m44s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.328.658	1.682.810.346.808	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h19m15s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.359.412	1.682.810.378.224	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h19m47s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.391.496	1.682.810.409.487	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h20m18s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.421.572	1.682.810.439.645	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h20m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.453.029	1.682.810.471.341	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h21m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.484.501	1.682.810.503.032	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h21m52s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.516.544	1.682.810.535.091	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h22m24s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.547.824	1.682.810.566.297	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h22m55s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.578.474	1.682.810.597.081	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h23m25s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.609.696	1.682.810.628.125	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h23m57s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.641.038	1.682.810.659.174	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h24m27s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.671.566	1.682.810.690.819	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h24m59s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.703.087	1.682.810.720.858	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h25m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.733.813	1.682.810.752.149	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h26m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682810765.63	1.682.810.784.177	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h26m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.796.295	1.682.810.814.762	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h27m03s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682810827.02	1.682.810.845.714	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h27m35s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.858.821	1682810877.14	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h28m06s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.890.551	1.682.810.908.668	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h28m37s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.921.473	1.682.810.940.158	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h29m09s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.810.953.485	1.682.810.971.938	45	23	27	23	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h29m40s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682810984.03	1.682.810.996.533	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h30m06s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.010.033	1.682.811.021.632	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h30m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682811033.98	1.682.811.045.662	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h30m55s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.058.894	1.682.811.070.533	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h31m19s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.083.189	1.682.811.096.367	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h31m45s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.109.546	1.682.811.121.024	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h32m10s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.134.433	1.682.811.146.715	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h32m35s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.159.674	1.682.811.171.263	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h33m00s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.184.628	1.682.811.196.302	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h33m25s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.209.553	1.682.811.221.075	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h33m50s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12			45	12	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h34m26s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.270.525	1.682.811.282.299	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h34m51s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12			45	12	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h35m27s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.331.588	1.682.811.343.133	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h35m50s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.354.428	1.682.811.366.363	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h36m15s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.379.154	1.682.811.390.912	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h36m39s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.403.642	1.682.811.415.133	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h37m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.428.597	1.682.811.440.148	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h37m29s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682811452.91	1.682.811.464.671	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h37m54s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682811477.68	1.682.811.489.573	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h38m18s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.502.317	1.682.811.513.698	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h38m42s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.526.859	1.682.811.538.777	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h39m06s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.549.556	1.682.811.560.921	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h39m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.574.041	1.682.811.585.499	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h39m54s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.598.917	1.682.811.611.068	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h40m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.623.887	1.682.811.635.394	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h40m45s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.648.968	1.682.811.660.487	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h41m09s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.673.755	1.682.811.685.143	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h41m34s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.697.942	1.682.811.710.059	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h41m59s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.722.935	1.682.811.734.506	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h42m24s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.748.021	1.682.811.763.649	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h42m53s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682811776.92	1.682.811.792.304	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h43m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.804.641	1.682.811.820.211	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h43m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.833.157	1.682.811.848.072	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h44m17s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.861.331	1.682.811.876.868	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h44m46s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.890.175	1.682.811.905.929	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h45m14s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.918.421	1682811934.21	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h45m43s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.947.797	1.682.811.963.546	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h46m12s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.811.976.413	1.682.811.992.281	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h46m41s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.005.059	1.682.812.021.018	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h47m10s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.034.458	1682812049.99	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h47m38s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.062.032	1.682.812.078.206	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h48m06s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.090.952	1.682.812.106.927	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h48m36s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.119.671	1.682.812.135.022	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h49m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.148.004	1.682.812.163.453	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h49m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.176.019	1.682.812.191.917	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h50m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.205.326	1.682.812.221.029	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h50m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.234.125	1.682.812.249.916	45	18	21	18	2	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 01h50m59s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.263.554	1.682.812.279.119	45	18	21	18	2</	

https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h00m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.836.818	1.682.812.858.914	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h01m08s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.873.405	1.682.812.894.459	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h01m43s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.907.342	1.682.812.928.323	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h02m17s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.941.711	1.682.812.962.356	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h02m51s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.812.975.254	1.682.812.995.857	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h03m25s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.009.355	1.682.813.030.124	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h03m58s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.042.676	1.682.813.063.155	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h04m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.075.759	1.682.813.095.783	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h05m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.109.621	1.682.813.130.347	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h05m38s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.142.706	1.682.813.163.356	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h06m12s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.176.876	1.682.813.197.615	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h06m46s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.210.601	1.682.813.231.195	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h07m20s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.244.876	1.682.813.265.382	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h07m54s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.278.637	1.682.813.298.957	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h08m27s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.311.927	1.682.813.332.722	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h09m01s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.345.551	1.682.813.366.536	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h09m35s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.380.004	1.682.813.400.373	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h10m08s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.412.872	1.682.813.433.687	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h10m42s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.446.848	1.682.813.467.391	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h11m16s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.480.512	1682813500.7	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h11m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.513.805	1.682.813.534.145	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h12m22s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.546.799	1.682.813.567.284	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h12m57s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.582.953	1.682.813.603.476	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h13m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.616.942	1.682.813.637.993	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h14m07s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.651.792	1.682.813.672.934	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h14m41s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.686.002	1.682.813.707.388	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h15m16s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.720.455	1.682.813.741.982	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h15m50s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.754.907	1.682.813.775.922	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h16m25s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.788.989	1.682.813.810.752	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h17m00s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682813824.24	1682813845.41	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h17m34s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.858.803	1.682.813.880.397	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h18m08s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.891.936	1.682.813.913.352	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h18m42s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.926.698	1682813948.21	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h19m16s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.960.772	1.682.813.982.234	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h19m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.813.993.926	1.682.814.015.462	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h20m24s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.028.476	1.682.814.049.512	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h20m58s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.062.401	1.682.814.083.824	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h21m32s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.096.754	1.682.814.118.097	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h22m06s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.130.566	1.682.814.152.113	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h22m40s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.164.269	1.682.814.185.251	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h23m13s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.198.056	1682814219.08	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h23m47s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.231.717	1.682.814.253.112	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h24m22s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.266.221	1.682.814.288.192	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h24m56s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.300.609	1682814322.21	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h25m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.335.237	1.682.814.356.914	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h26m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.368.103	1.682.814.389.493	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h26m38s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.402.974	1.682.814.424.075	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h27m13s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.437.702	1682814459.09	45	29	33	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h27m47s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682814471.98	1.682.814.493.108	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h28m22s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.506.719	1.682.814.528.048	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h28m56s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.540.525	1.682.814.562.454	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h29m31s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.575.813	1.682.814.596.767	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h30m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.609.529	1.682.814.631.471	45	29	33	29	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h30m40s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.644.298	1.682.814.655.842	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h31m05s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.669.472	1.682.814.681.064	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h31m30s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.694.494	1.682.814.706.392	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h31m53s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.718.008	1.682.814.729.561	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h32m18s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.742.567	1.682.814.754.144	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h32m43s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.767.601	1.682.814.779.366	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h33m08s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.792.718	1.682.814.804.409	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h33m33s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.817.508	1.682.814.828.913	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h33m57s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682814841.9	1.682.814.853.503	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h34m22s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.866.406	1.682.814.877.979	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h34m47s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.891.022	1682814902.68	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h35m11s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.915.924	1.682.814.927.823	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h35m37s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.941.407	1682814952.59	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h36m00s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.814.964.831	1.682.814.976.441	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h36m25s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682814989.6	1.682.815.001.373	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h36m49s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.013.618	1.682.815.025.192	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h37m14s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.038.169	1.682.815.049.627	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h37m38s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.062.192	1.682.815.073.448	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h38m02s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1682815086.66	1.682.815.098.001	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h38m26s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.110.176	1.682.815.122.066	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h38m51s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.134.962	1.682.815.146.237	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h39m15s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.159.535	1.682.815.171.095	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h39m40s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.184.281	1.682.815.195.504	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h40m04s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.208.712	1.682.815.220.104	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h40m29s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.233.976	1.682.815.245.523	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h40m54s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.815.258.968	1.682.815.270.398	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h41m19s	1,68281E+12	1,68281E+12	1.682.							

https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h51m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.815.870.007	1.682.815.889.086	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h51m37s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.815.901.004	1.682.815.920.099	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h52m08s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.815.932.295	1.682.815.951.332	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h52m39s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.815.963.585	1682815983.02	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h53m12s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682815996.65	1.682.816.015.756	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h53m44s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682816028.77	1.682.816.048.695	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h54m17s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.061.256	1.682.816.080.759	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h54m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.093.801	1.682.816.113.023	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h55m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.126.744	1.682.816.146.371	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h55m54s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.159.146	1682816179.12	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h56m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.192.487	1.682.816.211.402	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h57m00s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.224.183	1.682.816.243.563	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h57m33s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682816256.85	1.682.816.276.639	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h58m06s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682816290.17	1.682.816.309.135	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h58m38s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.322.379	1.682.816.341.648	45	25	29	25	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h59m10s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.355.045	1.682.816.375.152	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 02h59m43s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682816387.22	1.682.816.408.967	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h00m17s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.421.398	1.682.816.441.794	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h00m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.454.058	1.682.816.476.923	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h01m26s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.491.182	1.682.816.516.656	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h02m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.529.288	1.682.816.550.189	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h02m38s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.562.439	1.682.816.583.627	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h03m13s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.598.131	1.682.816.618.681	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h03m48s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.632.504	1.682.816.652.994	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h04m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.666.603	1.682.816.687.135	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h04m55s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.699.781	1.682.816.720.036	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h05m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.732.732	1.682.816.753.463	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h06m02s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.766.683	1682816787.01	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h06m35s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.799.428	1.682.816.819.745	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h07m08s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.831.825	1.682.816.852.808	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h07m40s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.864.897	1.682.816.885.607	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h08m14s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.898.676	1.682.816.918.765	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h08m47s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.931.398	1.682.816.951.749	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h09m20s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.965.054	1.682.816.985.312	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h09m54s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.816.997.796	1.682.817.018.111	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h10m26s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.030.413	1.682.817.051.125	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h10m59s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682817063.65	1.682.817.083.845	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h11m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.096.898	1.682.817.116.989	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h12m06s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.130.287	1.682.817.150.341	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h12m39s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.163.663	1.682.817.184.223	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h13m12s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.197.124	1.682.817.217.475	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h13m46s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682817230.71	1.682.817.250.614	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h14m18s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.262.667	1.682.817.283.089	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h14m51s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.295.468	1.682.817.315.588	45	26	30	26	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h15m24s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.328.406	1.682.817.344.958	45	26	21	17	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h15m53s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.357.432	1682817375.76	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h16m25s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.389.199	1.682.817.407.638	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h16m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.420.487	1.682.817.438.717	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h17m27s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682817451.67	1.682.817.469.493	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h17m57s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.481.797	1.682.817.500.311	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h18m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.513.957	1.682.817.531.582	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h19m00s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.544.427	1.682.817.562.781	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h19m31s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.575.484	1.682.817.593.732	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h20m02s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.606.639	1.682.817.624.381	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h20m33s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.638.128	1.682.817.656.265	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h21m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.669.985	1.682.817.688.178	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h21m36s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.701.183	1.682.817.718.868	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h22m07s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.732.046	1.682.817.749.975	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h22m38s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.762.717	1.682.817.780.605	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h23m09s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.793.339	1.682.817.811.464	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h23m39s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.824.163	1.682.817.842.621	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h24m11s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.855.668	1.682.817.873.778	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h24m42s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.887.081	1.682.817.905.221	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h25m14s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.918.462	1.682.817.936.482	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h25m44s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.949.053	1.682.817.967.159	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h26m16s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.817.980.381	1.682.817.998.782	45	22	26	21	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h26m47s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.011.897	1.682.818.030.112	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h27m18s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.043.091	1.682.818.061.484	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h27m50s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.074.706	1.682.818.093.037	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h28m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682818106.39	1.682.818.124.176	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h28m53s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.137.565	1.682.818.155.754	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h29m24s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.168.513	1.682.818.186.426	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h29m54s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12			45	22	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h30m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.235.903	1.682.818.253.568	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h31m01s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.265.744	1.682.818.283.684	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h31m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682818296.11	1.682.818.309.799	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h31m59s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.323.685	1682818337.41	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h32m26s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.350.194	1.682.818.364.971	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h32m54s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.378.467	1.682.818.392.251	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h33m21s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.405.415	1.682.818.419.296	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h33m48s	1,6828									

https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h41m50s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.915.014	1682818928.88	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h42m18s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.942.159	1.682.818.956.037	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h42m44s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.969.041	1.682.818.982.865	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h43m10s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.818.994.716	1.682.819.008.475	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h43m36s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.020.583	1.682.819.034.323	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h44m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.047.637	1.682.819.061.505	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h44m30s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.075.092	1.682.819.088.829	45	16	19	16	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h44m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.100.876	1.682.819.121.746	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h45m31s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.135.658	1.682.819.156.826	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h46m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.169.939	1.682.819.190.811	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h46m39s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682819203.28	1.682.819.224.499	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h47m13s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.237.382	1.682.819.258.355	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h47m47s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.271.767	1.682.819.292.926	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h48m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.305.856	1.682.819.326.894	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h48m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.340.347	1.682.819.361.286	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h49m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.373.672	1.682.819.394.334	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h50m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.407.814	1.682.819.428.647	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h50m37s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.441.789	1.682.819.462.851	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h51m11s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.475.397	1.682.819.495.823	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h51m44s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682819508.49	1.682.819.529.324	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h52m17s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.541.592	1.682.819.562.394	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h52m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.574.167	1.682.819.594.873	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h53m23s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.607.666	1.682.819.628.297	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h53m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.640.463	1.682.819.661.328	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h54m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.673.456	1682819694.04	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h55m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.708.498	1682819729.3	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h55m38s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.742.446	1.682.819.763.443	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h56m12s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.777.439	1.682.819.798.241	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h56m46s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.810.771	1.682.819.832.118	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h57m20s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12			45	28	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h57m58s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.882.809	1682819903.45	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h58m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.916.444	1.682.819.937.136	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h59m06s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.950.977	1.682.819.971.848	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 03h59m40s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.819.984.365	1.682.820.005.701	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h00m13s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.017.811	1.682.820.038.874	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h00m47s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.051.944	1.682.820.072.923	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h01m21s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.086.088	1.682.820.107.299	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h01m55s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.119.615	1.682.820.140.533	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h02m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682820153.03	1682820173.66	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h03m02s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.187.073	1.682.820.207.732	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h03m37s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.221.499	1.682.820.242.083	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h04m10s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.254.828	1.682.820.275.082	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h04m44s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.288.305	1.682.820.308.881	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h05m17s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.321.214	1.682.820.342.303	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h05m51s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.356.037	1.682.820.376.711	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h06m24s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.388.639	1.682.820.408.807	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h06m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.421.335	1.682.820.441.935	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h07m31s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.455.289	1.682.820.475.715	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h08m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.489.055	1.682.820.509.482	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h08m38s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.522.728	1.682.820.543.251	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h09m10s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.554.617	1.682.820.575.142	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h09m44s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.588.514	1.682.820.608.895	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h10m16s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.621.347	1.682.820.641.612	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h10m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.654.009	1.682.820.674.739	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h11m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.687.205	1.682.820.707.928	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h11m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.720.226	1.682.820.740.273	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h12m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.754.206	1.682.820.774.219	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h13m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.787.354	1.682.820.807.204	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h13m35s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.819.689	1.682.820.840.009	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h14m09s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.853.268	1.682.820.874.136	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h14m42s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.887.206	1.682.820.907.467	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h15m15s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.920.007	1.682.820.940.326	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h15m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.953.522	1.682.820.974.096	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h16m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.820.986.464	1.682.821.006.817	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h16m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.020.047	1.682.821.040.131	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h17m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.052.804	1.682.821.073.523	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h18m02s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.086.851	1.682.821.107.115	45	27	31	27	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h18m35s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.120.137	1.682.821.134.829	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h19m04s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.148.534	1.682.821.163.043	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h19m31s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.175.601	1.682.821.190.137	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h19m58s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.202.924	1.682.821.217.767	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h20m26s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.230.897	1.682.821.246.109	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h20m55s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.259.681	1.682.821.274.625	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h21m23s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.287.974	1.682.821.303.064	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h21m52s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682821316.71	1.682.821.333.543	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h22m21s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.345.787	1.682.821.361.034	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h22m50s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.374.909	1.682.821.389.285	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h23m18s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.402.902	1.682.821.417.621	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h23m46s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.430.917	1.682.821.445.734	45	17	20	17	2	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30 04h24m14s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.821.458.803	1.						

https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h33m16s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.000.648	1.682.822.021.219	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h33m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12			45	28	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h34m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.072.716	1.682.822.093.787	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h35m02s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.107.346	1.682.822.127.991	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h35m36s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.140.707	1.682.822.161.789	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h36m09s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.173.987	1.682.822.194.799	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h36m42s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.206.499	1.682.822.227.632	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h37m15s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.239.624	1.682.822.260.643	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h37m48s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.272.525	1.682.822.293.362	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h38m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.306.369	1.682.822.327.092	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h38m55s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.340.278	1.682.822.361.512	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h39m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.374.074	1.682.822.394.967	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h40m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.407.949	1.682.822.428.734	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h40m37s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.441.566	1.682.822.462.317	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h41m11s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.475.915	1682822496.83	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h41m45s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.509.553	1.682.822.530.612	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h42m19s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.543.383	1.682.822.564.161	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h42m52s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.577.257	1.682.822.597.883	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h43m26s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.610.754	1.682.822.631.335	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h44m00s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682822644.58	1.682.822.665.949	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h44m34s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.679.078	1682822699.87	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h45m08s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.712.549	1682822733.46	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h45m41s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682822746.14	1.682.822.767.185	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h46m15s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682822780.2	1.682.822.801.719	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h46m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682822813.82	1.682.822.834.658	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h47m23s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.847.421	1.682.822.867.939	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h47m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.881.231	1.682.822.901.343	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h48m30s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.914.807	1.682.822.935.926	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h49m04s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.949.245	1.682.822.969.989	45	28	32	28	3	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h49m38s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.822.982.776	1.682.822.994.315	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h50m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.007.686	1.682.823.019.303	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h50m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.032.753	1.682.823.044.007	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h50m52s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.056.941	1682823068.34	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h51m16s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.080.666	1.682.823.092.195	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h51m41s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.105.771	1.682.823.117.244	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h52m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.129.107	1682823140.53	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h52m28s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.152.543	1.682.823.163.838	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h52m52s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.176.912	1.682.823.188.307	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h53m16s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.200.437	1.682.823.212.059	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h53m40s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.224.603	1.682.823.236.234	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h54m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.249.936	1.682.823.261.496	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h54m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682823273.66	1.682.823.285.153	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h54m53s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.297.666	1.682.823.308.286	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h55m16s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.321.409	1.682.823.332.721	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h55m40s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.344.701	1.682.823.355.968	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h56m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.370.304	1.682.823.382.512	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h56m30s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.395.154	1.682.823.406.595	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h56m54s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12			45	12	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h57m30s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.455.193	1682823466.69	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h57m55s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.479.464	1.682.823.491.308	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h58m19s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.504.413	1.682.823.515.755	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h58m43s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.527.153	1.682.823.538.426	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h59m07s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.551.828	1.682.823.563.257	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h59m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682823576.95	1.682.823.588.568	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 04h59m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.601.453	1.682.823.613.056	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h00m20s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.625.199	1.682.823.636.915	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h00m45s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682823649.51	1.682.823.660.998	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h01m10s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.674.342	1.682.823.686.123	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h01m34s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.699.014	1.682.823.710.778	45	12	14	12	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h01m59s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.723.743	1.682.823.734.063	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h02m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.746.847	1.682.823.757.637	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h02m45s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.770.026	1.682.823.780.501	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h03m09s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.793.768	1.682.823.804.343	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h03m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.817.291	1.682.823.827.459	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h03m56s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.840.555	1.682.823.851.215	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h04m19s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.863.538	1.682.823.873.894	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h04m42s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682823886.53	1.682.823.896.852	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h05m05s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.909.868	1.682.823.920.321	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h05m29s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.934.297	1.682.823.945.051	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h05m53s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.823.957.549	1.682.823.968.421	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h06m17s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682823981.98	1.682.823.992.461	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h06m40s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.004.912	1.682.824.015.271	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h07m04s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.028.657	1.682.824.039.126	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h07m27s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.051.678	1.682.824.062.319	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h07m49s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682824074.01	1.682.824.084.305	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h08m13s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682824097.82	1.682.824.108.431	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h08m37s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.122.027	1.682.824.132.624	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h09m01s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682824145.64	1.682.824.156.355	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h09m23s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.168.447	1.682.824.179.074	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2023-04-30 05h09m48s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.192.549	1.682.824.203.195	45	10	12	10	1	yes
https://we short_text human_sti Human str 2										

https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h18m22s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.706.765	1.682.824.724.742	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h18m52s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12			45	22	45	-6	41	no
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h19m30s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682824775.22	1.682.824.793.513	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h20m02s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.806.981	1.682.824.824.979	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h20m32s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1682824837.15	1.682.824.855.285	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h21m03s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.868.206	1.682.824.885.661	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h21m34s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.898.734	1.682.824.917.509	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h22m06s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.930.639	1682824948.35	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h22m36s	1,68282E+12	1,68282E+12	1.682.824.961.082	1.682.824.979.014	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h23m07s	1,68282E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.824.992.307	1.682.825.010.555	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h23m38s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.023.012	1.682.825.041.124	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h24m09s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.053.907	1.682.825.071.719	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h24m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682825084.12	1.682.825.102.834	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h25m12s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.116.543	1.682.825.134.612	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h25m42s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.147.237	1.682.825.165.532	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h26m14s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.178.409	1.682.825.196.991	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h26m44s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.209.172	1.682.825.227.244	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h27m16s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.240.635	1.682.825.258.858	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h27m47s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.272.334	1.682.825.290.734	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h28m18s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.302.675	1.682.825.321.108	45	22	26	22	3	yes
https://we short_text human_str Human str 2023-04-30_05h28m50s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1.682.825.334.763	1.682.825.352.358	45	22	26	22	3	yes

URL	application name	application version	strategy	start datetime	timestamp TESTAR start	timestamp TESTAR end	timestamp server start	timestamp server end	action limit	number of fields	actions executed	number of fields filled	actions per field	submit
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h30m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682825406.33	1,682.825.414.021	45	12	7	5	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h30m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682825426.34	1,682.825.445.459	45	12	30	10	6	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h30m54s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682.825.459.065	1,682.825.467.322	45	12	8	4	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h31m15s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.480.194	1,682.825.491.669	45	12	14	7	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h31m40s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.505.016	1,682.825.528.794	45	12	43	10	9	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h32m16s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.540.861	1,682.825.548.218	45	12	6	4	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h32m36s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.561.232	1,682.825.572.372	45	12	13	8	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h33m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.585.947	1,682.825.598.567	45	12	17	7	7	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h33m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.611.381	1,682.825.631.548	45	12	33	12	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h33m59s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.643.914	1,682.825.652.612	45	12	9	4	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h34m21s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.665.843	1,682.825.671.802	45	12	4	2	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h34m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.684.264	1,682.825.693.205	45	12	9	5	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h35m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682825705.54	1,682.825.715.044	45	12	10	5	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h35m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.726.931	1,682.825.746.347	45	12	32	12	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h35m55s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.759.318	1,682.825.766.382	45	12	6	3	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h36m14s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.779.227	1,682.825.792.787	45	12	19	8	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h36m40s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.805.108	1,682.825.821.228	45	12	23	10	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h37m09s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.834.277	1,682.825.844.284	45	12	12	5	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h37m31s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.856.145	1,682.825.862.465	45	12	5	3	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h37m51s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.876.254	1,682.825.881.717	45	12	3	1	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h38m09s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.894.289	1,682.825.902.386	45	12	8	2	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h38m30s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.915.083	1,682.825.919.821	45	12	2	0	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h38m48s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.932.439	1,682.825.940.907	45	12	8	4	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h39m08s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.952.67	1,682.825.958.719	45	12	4	2	1	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h39m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.825.970.812	1,682.825.984.673	45	12	20	10	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h39m52s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682825996.65	1,682.826.006.566	45	12	11	6	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h40m14s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.019.112	1,682.826.035.632	45	12	25	9	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h40m44s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682826048.85	1,682.826.064.312	45	12	22	8	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h41m12s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.077.205	1,682.826.091.801	45	12	19	8	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h41m40s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.104.819	1,682.826.120.994	45	12	24	12	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h42m09s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682826134.51	1,682.826.148.559	45	17	19	11	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h42m36s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.160.489	1,682.826.177.105	45	17	24	10	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h43m05s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.190.380	1,682.826.210.595	45	17	33	10	6	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h43m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.223.684	1682826234.75	45	17	13	7	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h44m02s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.247.346	1,682.826.266.043	45	17	29	12	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h44m34s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.279.317	1,682.826.291.582	45	17	16	10	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h44m59s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	17	45	-6	5	no	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h45m37s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.342.184	1,682.826.363.863	45	17	35	10	8	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h46m12s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.376.555	1,682.826.387.902	45	17	13	8	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h46m36s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	17	45	-6	8	no	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h47m14s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.438.745	1,682.826.451.204	45	17	16	7	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h47m38s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.463.424	1,682.826.472.695	45	17	9	4	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h48m00s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.484.997	1,682.826.496.308	45	17	13	8	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h48m24s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	17	45	-6	6	no	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h49m03s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.548.437	1,682.826.558.707	45	17	11	8	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h49m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.571.471	1,682.826.592.732	45	17	35	8	9	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h50m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.605.693	1,682.826.615.157	45	17	10	4	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h50m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.627.372	1,682.826.638.694	45	17	13	6	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h50m47s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	17	45	-6	6	no	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h51m25s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682826689.78	1,682.826.713.249	45	17	41	13	9	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h52m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.725.697	1,682.826.741.595	45	17	22	8	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h52m29s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.754.207	1,682.826.766.943	45	17	16	6	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h52m54s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.779.308	1,682.826.792.692	45	17	18	8	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h53m20s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	17	45	-6	8	no	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h53m58s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682826843.2	1,682.826.854.675	45	17	14	8	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h54m23s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.867.915	1,682.826.876.102	45	17	7	4	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h54m43s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.887.858	1,682.826.903.433	45	17	22	9	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h55m12s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.916.698	1,682.826.928.541	45	17	14	7	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h55m37s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	17	45	-6	15	no	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h56m16s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.826.981.386	1,682.826.993.612	45	17	15	10	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h56m41s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.005.782	1,682.827.011.011	45	15	3	0	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h56m59s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.024.015	1682827030.42	45	15	5	2	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h57m18s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.043.399	1,682.827.053.055	45	15	10	6	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h57m40s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.065.505	1,682.827.075.255	45	15	11	5	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h58m03s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.088.023	1,682.827.094.203	45	15	4	1	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h58m21s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682827106.25	1,682.827.122.748	45	15	25	10	7	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h58m50s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.135.459	1,682.827.146.593	45	15	14	7	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h59m15s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.160.377	1,682.827.169.262	45	15	9	5	2	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 05h59m37s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.182.121	1,682.827.199.985	45	15	28	11	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 06h00m08s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.213.106	1,682.827.234.015	45	15	33	12	5	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 06h00m41s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.246.573	1,682.827.256.433	45	15	11	5	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 06h01m05s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.269.714	1,682.827.288.784	45	15	31	11	6	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 06h01m37s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.301.858	1,682.827.314.459	45	15	16	7	3	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 06h02m03s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.328.073	1,682.827.348.241	45	15	13	14	6	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30 06h02m37s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.827.361.897	1,6							

https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h10m30s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12		45	27	45	-6	4	yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h11m09s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.474.521	1,682.831.491.683	45	27	23	16	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h11m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.504.791	1,682.831.519.874	45	27	19	13	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h12m08s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.533.133	1,682.831.544.026	45	27	12	7	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h12m31s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.556.025	1,682.831.571.945	45	27	21	10	5	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h12m59s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h13m38s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.623.613	1,682.831.637.013	45	27	17	10	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h14m04s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.649.702	1,682.831.664.3	45	27	19	10	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h14m32s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.677.186	1,682.831.690.863	45	27	17	12	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h14m59s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	9	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h15m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.743.969	1,682.831.762.845	45	27	28	14	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h16m10s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h16m51s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.815.979	1,682.831.830.102	45	27	18	10	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h17m19s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.844.355	1,682.831.857.666	45	27	16	10	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h17m45s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.870.237	1,682.831.891.135	45	27	32	13	6	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h18m19s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.904.413	1,682.831.919.59	45	27	29	16	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h18m51s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	12	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h19m29s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.974.384	1,682.831.986.438	45	27	14	8	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h19m54s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.831.999.01	1,682.832.017.124	45	27	27	14	5	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h20m24s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	6	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h21m03s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h21m41s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	5	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h22m21s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.146.256	1,682.832.167.554	45	27	33	17	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h22m55s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h23m34s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.219.213	1,682.832.242.228	45	27	38	14	6	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h24m09s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.254.562	1,682.832.270.813	45	27	23	13	6	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h24m37s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	4	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h25m16s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	27	45	-6	8	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h25m56s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.261.0	1,682.832.373.487	45	27	16	5	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h26m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.386.641	1,682.832.407.878	45	27	33	15	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h26m55s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.420.174	1,682.832.438.774	45	18	29	10	5	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h27m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.451.482	1,682.832.458.299	45	18	5	2	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h27m46s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	5	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h28m25s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.509.913	1,682.832.520.145	45	18	11	4	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h28m47s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.532.576	1,682.832.541.582	45	18	8	5	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h29m08s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h29m46s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h30m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.631.325	1,682.832.640.581	45	18	9	5	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h30m48s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.653.593	1,682.832.670.658	45	18	26	8	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h31m17s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.682.692	1,682.832.690.558	45	18	7	2	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h31m38s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.702.933	1,682.832.714.99	45	18	14	6	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h32m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.726.84	1,682.832.734.645	45	18	7	4	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h32m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h33m02s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.787.104	1,682.832.797.637	45	18	11	5	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h33m25s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.810.207	1,682.832.823.881	45	18	18	7	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h33m50s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	12	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h34m29s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.874.354	1,682.832.885.453	45	18	12	7	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h34m53s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	5	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h35m33s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.928.39	1,682.832.950.573	45	18	15	6	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h35m59s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.832.963.999	1,682.832.987.766	45	18	40	9	9	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h36m35s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	5	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h37m14s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.039.284	1,682.833.048.463	45	18	9	4	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h37m35s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.060.704	1,682.833.068.339	45	18	6	3	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h37m55s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.080.548	1,682.833.091.158	45	18	11	6	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h38m19s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.104.326	1,682.833.111.403	45	18	6	3	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h38m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.124.805	1,682.833.138.279	45	18	17	11	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h39m06s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.150.952	1,682.833.158.915	45	18	7	3	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h39m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	5	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h40m04s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h40m43s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	18	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h41m21s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.286.823	1,682.833.293.535	45	10	6	3	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h41m41s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12			45	10	45	-6	12	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h42m19s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.344.869	1,682.833.355.975	45	10	13	6	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h42m43s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.368.405	1,682.833.375.742	45	10	5	3	1	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h43m03s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.388.737	1,682.833.398.68	45	10	11	6	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h43m26s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.411.801	1,682.833.424.509	45	10	17	6	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h43m52s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.437.372	1,682.833.447.791	45	10	12	5	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h44m17s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.462.019	1,682.833.476.494	45	10	21	7	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h44m45s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.489.984	1,682.833.498.362	45	10	8	5	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h45m06s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.511.312	1,682.833.521.147	45	10	11	6	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h45m29s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.533.894	1,682.833.539.545	45	10	4	2	1	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h45m47s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.552.843	1,682.833.567.046	45	10	20	9	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h46m15s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.580.463	1,682.833.592.501	45	10	15	7	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h46m40s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.604.824	1,682.833.614.298	45	10	8	4	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h47m03s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.628.023	1,682.833.634.893	45	10	6	2	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h47m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.647.395	1,682.833.659.907	45	10	16	8	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h47m49s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.674.016	1,682.833.687.237	45	10	18	8	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h48m15s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.700.364	1,682.833.710.786	45	10	12	7	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_07h48m39s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.833.723.947	1,682.833.737.1						

https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h03m35s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	8 no		
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h04m15s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	8 no		
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h04m54s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	11 no		
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h05m33s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	9 no		
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h06m12s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	4 no		
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h06m52s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.834.816.512	1,682.834.835.135	45	29	16	3 yes	
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h07m22s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1682834847.36	1,682.834.873.669	45	29	45	11	6 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h08m01s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	4 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h08m40s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,682.834.925.689	1682834947.89	45	29	35	19	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h09m15s	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	1,68283E+12	45	29	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h09m55s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	29	45	-6	8 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h10m34s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.039.117	1,682.835.052.491	45	29	17	10	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h10m59s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.064.901	1,682.835.084.365	45	29	28	16	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h11m32s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.097.152	1,682.835.116.248	45	21	28	14	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h12m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	21	45	-6	7 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h12m44s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1682835169.48	1,682.835.182.368	45	21	15	9	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h13m10s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.195.889	1,682.835.206.499	45	21	11	3	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h13m34s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.219.507	1,682.835.229.346	45	21	10	5	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h13m57s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.242.339	1,682.835.260.699	45	21	27	14	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h14m27s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.272.012	1,682.835.283.476	45	21	13	7	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h14m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	21	45	-6	12 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h15m29s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.334.879	1,682.835.345.851	45	21	12	6	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h15m53s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.358.491	1,682.835.369.357	45	21	12	5	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h16m17s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.382.393	1,682.835.400.595	45	21	26	17	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h16m48s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.413.448	1,682.835.426.509	45	21	15	6	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h17m14s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.439.185	1,682.835.451.749	45	21	16	9	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h17m40s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.464.827	1,682.835.474.546	45	21	10	7	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h18m03s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	21	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h18m40s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.525.748	1,682.835.536.441	45	21	11	7	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h19m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.548.511	1,682.835.569.022	45	21	32	9	5 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h19m36s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	21	45	-6	8 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h20m15s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.619.686	1,682.835.632.318	45	21	15	8	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h20m39s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.644.897	1,682.835.653.757	45	21	8	4	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h21m02s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.667.449	1,682.835.686.166	45	21	28	15	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h21m33s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	21	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h22m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	21	45	-6	7 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h22m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1682835775.74	1,682.835.794.525	45	21	27	11	5 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h23m22s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.807.417	1682835817.41	45	21	11	4	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h23m44s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.829.607	1,682.835.844.547	45	21	20	11	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h24m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.857.639	1682835865.72	45	21	7	3	2 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h24m33s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.877.976	1,682.835.898.468	45	21	31	16	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h25m07s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.911.859	1,682.835.923.588	45	21	12	6	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h25m31s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.835.921.828	1,682.835.951.085	45	21	20	11	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h25m59s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	13 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h26m37s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.002.355	1,682.836.019.906	45	23	24	13	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h27m07s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.032.891	1682836045.73	45	23	15	7	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h27m33s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	6 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h28m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h28m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.135.987	1,682.836.143.305	45	23	6	2	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h29m10s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	6 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h29m48s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	4 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h30m27s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.232.772	1,682.836.243.252	45	23	11	6	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h30m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h31m30s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h32m10s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.335.181	1,682.836.356.572	45	23	34	17	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h32m44s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.369.726	1,682.836.385.671	45	23	23	6	6 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h33m14s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.398.604	1,682.836.415.115	45	23	24	12	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h33m43s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	4 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h34m21s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h35m00s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.505.115	1,682.836.520.434	45	23	21	8	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h35m28s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.533.257	1,682.836.547.106	45	23	18	10	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h35m55s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	6 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h36m34s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	7 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h37m12s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	6 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h37m51s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.676.459	1682836687.99	45	23	13	6	8 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h38m16s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h38m54s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	6 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h39m34s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.779.499	1,682.836.803.929	45	23	41	19	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h40m11s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.816.501	1,682.836.840.478	45	23	40	19	7 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h40m47s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.852.843	1,682.836.869.941	45	23	23	15	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h41m17s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.882.809	1682836898.01	45	23	21	11	3 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h41m46s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	5 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h42m24s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	9 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h43m04s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.836.989.112	1,682.837.013.014	45	23	40	16	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h43m41s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.837.026.117	1,682.837.050.241	45	23	41	14	5 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h44m17s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.837.062.809	1,682.837.080.592	45	23	25	10	6 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h44m48s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.837.093.524	1,682.837.111.941	45	23	26	13	4 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h45m20s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	7 yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h45m58s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	45	23	45	-6	10 no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30_08h46m37s	1,68284E+12	1,68284E+12	1,682.837.202.631	1,68					

https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h44m41s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.487.094	1.682.851.493.447	45	10	5	3	1	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h45m00s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.505.894	1.682.851.511.85	45	10	4	1	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h45m18s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	10	45	-6	9	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h45m57s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682851562.85	1.682.851.573.795	45	10	12	7	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h46m20s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.586.004	1.682.851.593.893	45	10	7	3	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h46m41s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682851606.31	1.682.851.610.943	45	10	2	0	1	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h46m58s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	10	45	-6	8	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h47m36s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	10	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h48m15s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.701.014	1.682.851.710.164	45	10	9	6	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h48m37s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.723.179	1.682.851.735.781	45	10	15	7	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h49m03s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.748.935	1.682.851.769.729	45	10	34	10	6	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h49m37s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.783.642	1.682.851.796.806	45	10	16	7	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h50m04s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.810.121	1.682.851.820.924	45	10	12	5	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h50m27s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.833.263	1.682.851.840.263	45	10	5	2	2	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h50m46s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.852.271	1.682.851.862.018	45	10	10	5	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h51m09s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.874.833	1.682.851.881.982	45	10	6	4	1	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h51m29s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	10	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h52m09s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.851.934.937	1.682.851.946.909	45	10	15	6	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h52m33s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h53m12s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	8	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h53m52s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	4	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h54m32s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.077.473	1.682.852.089.244	45	22	13	8	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h54m56s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h55m36s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	8	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h56m17s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h56m56s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	9	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h57m36s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	15	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h58m17s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	7	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h58m57s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	8	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	12h59m36s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.382.184	1.682.852.403.96	45	22	32	14	6	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h00m11s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.417.344	1.682.852.432.868	45	22	21	9	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h00m39s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.445.735	1.682.852.457.867	45	22	14	6	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h01m06s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.471.597	1.682.852.488.146	45	22	22	10	4	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h01m34s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.500.586	1.682.852.513.105	45	22	15	8	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h02m00s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.526.127	1.682.852.538.608	45	22	14	9	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h02m26s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	6	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h03m05s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.590.908	1.682.852.606.419	45	22	20	12	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h03m33s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	14	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h04m13s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682852659.4	1.682.852.685.471	45	22	44	12	7	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h04m51s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1682852696.96	1.682.852.712.739	45	22	21	11	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h05m20s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.726.038	1.682.852.752.052	45	22	44	17	7	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h05m59s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.765.348	1.682.852.782.407	45	22	23	14	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h06m30s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.795.956	1.682.852.813.704	45	22	26	13	5	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h07m01s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	8	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h07m41s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.867.194	1.682.852.878.127	45	22	11	4	3	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h08m04s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	5	no
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h08m45s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12	1.682.852.930.464	1.682.852.946.702	45	22	21	11	5	yes
https://we short_text	random	Random	2023-04-30	13h09m15s	1,68285E+12	1,68285E+12			45	22	45	-6	6	no